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Cytochrome complex alterations during TE specification in human embryonic development.

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We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We identify and characterize here changes in cytochrome complex composition during TE specification in human embryonic development.